

UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS

THE EFFECTS OF PROMPT CLAIMS SETTLEMENT ON THE SALES OF COMPREHENSIVE MOTOR INSURANCE POLICIES IN NIGERIA.

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research project titled: “**THE EFFECTS OF PROMPT CLAIM SETTLEMENT ON THE SALES OF COMPREHENSIVE MOTOR INSURANCE POLICIES IN NIGERIA**” was written by ODESANYA MISTURAH ABIMBOLA with matriculation number: **100207106** of the department of Actuarial science and Insurance, Faculty of Business Administration under the supervision of Dr. S.A. Aduloju.

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ABSTRACT

Claims settlement, which dates as far back as the history of insurance, is the only reason the consumer (insured) buys an insurance product. The fast administration of Claims is therefore not only a legal obligation of an insurance firm, but a strong public relations and marketing strategy. The response to claims has rather been slow in Nigeria and this is of great concern, since a thriving economy depends to a large extent on the guarantees and assurances received from insurance companies.

This research investigated the trends in the sample company's claims settlement system and its effect on the sales and marketing of its insurance products. The objectives of the research were to;

- 1 To show the relationship between prompt claims settlement and purchase of insurance.
- 2 To find out if claim settlement period falls within the period prescribed by the law.
- 3 To find out if the company has complaint service unit.

Data collection was conducted by administering questionnaires to both customers and staff of the company. The results obtained from the data collection were cross tabulated and subjected to descriptive analysis. The results obtained established the fact that prompt and satisfactory claims payment had positive effects on the sales and marketing of insurance products and vice versa.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The concept of insurance services is not a new phenomenon to the citizens of Nigeria. This is because of the nature of the extended family unit and communal practices in the areas. For instance, an individual or group in the community may suffer loss either through theft, flood disaster, farm destruction by pest or flood, fire disaster, death, accident, or any form of loss. The immediate extended family and or some members of the community who are friends or neighbors will quickly come to sympathize and support the person by way of gifts and personal donations. In order to help reduce the suffering, which is restoring or putting back the insured to the position he was before suffering a loss. This role was gradually taken over by insurance industry in our modern society (Garba and Abdulsalam, 2011). This action could better be described as a traditional way of indemnity, which is restoring or putting back the insured in the position he was before suffering a loss. This role was gradually taken over by insurance industry in our modern society.

Bickelhaupt (1983) sees the insurer as performing several basic functions consisting of product design (insurance policy), marketing, underwriting, and loss payments. Loss payment which is Claims settlement is perhaps the most obvious of the important functions of insurance. Loss payment is the primary reason for and the result of many insurance contracts because uncertainty about losses creates the need for insurance (Aduloju, 2008).

The performance of Nigeria insurance industry is sub-optimal. Insurance density stood at 6.9% industry global ranking was 61 and gross premium income was naira 180bn in 2008 (NAICOM, 2010). According to National Insurance Commission (NAICOM, 2008), the industry has the potential to deliver 1.3 trillion naira (US\$7.5bn) in gross premium by 2012 and 60 trillion naira (US\$400.81bn) by 2020. NAICOM also targeted increased insurance penetration from the current 6% to 30% in 2021, grow insurance contribution to GDP from 0.7% to 3% in 2012, and grow insurance density from the present 1,200naira per individual to 7500naira (Augustine and Nwanneka, 2011).

A survey conducted by the NOI Polls Limited has identified lack of awareness and public enlightenment on the benefits of insurance as factors responsible for the low level of insurance penetration in the country. It also said while 86 per cent of Nigerians do not have any form of insurance cover, nine per cent of them do not trust insurance service providers and that motor vehicle insurance account for 63 per cent of insurance sales in the country (*Thisday Newspaper of 28, August 2013*).

The rising intricacy of the world economic system in today's industrial age has increased the importance of insurance in the process of manufacturing and profit-making dealings. The absence of insurance will constantly subject the individual/organization to the fear of a huge financial loss in the event of a tragedy and so will affect their decision-making course of action in diverse ways. It is therefore apparent that a viable economy is dependent on insurance company being swift in compensating victims of an insurance claim. One of the principal functions of insurance is settlement of claims. It is in fact the worry that a loss might occur that persuades individuals and economic distribution to take up insurance

policies. Claims settlement is the monetary compensation that is paid to the policyholder in the event of a loss (Parsons, 2005).

It used to be said that insurers will do anything possible to squirm out of paying claims. Insurers have been criticized for their marketing methods based on the cloudiness, twisting and mis-selling. If a company does not effectively handle its claims service, it can tarnish its image hence affect the sales and marketing of their insurance products. Insurance company's attitude to claims settlements has in the past provoked a lot of public criticism and even attracted the attention of governments.

In the past, majority of insurers have persistently failed to recognize the need for qualified staff or claims specialists to enhance to enhance their claims service. The typical claims department always seemed to be an afterthought, the last to get new equipment or staff. The focus was on sales, winning new business and retaining accounts. As the years passed there have been a very few changes in the perception of claims (Burley, 2008).

It is in this light that most insurance regulatory bodies now seek to recognize the need for a thorough review of the role of the claims professional in the insurance industry (Kelly, 2008).

Consequently, the reputation of any insurance company and consumers demand for insurance depends, to a large extent, on the sort of claims services provided by the company to its customers.

Prompt claims settlement is surely the way, to a large extent. This being the case, it is peremptory that these insurance companies make a commitment to claims handling.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In Nigeria, just like any other insurance companies in other parts of the world pay claims, yet have a dented image in the eyes of the insuring public (Lijadu, 2002). The difficulty in running an effective claims settlement management that would satisfy the customers and earn their confidence as well as cause them to purchase insurance products has remained too long in the insurance industry in the sub-region and the world at large.

The general perception of an average Nigerian is that the insurance companies are only quick to collect premiums but slow in settling claims. This belief by many has resulted in low patronage of insurance companies by Nigerians. Many firms in the industry have been accused of unethical behaviors such as non-payment of claims, a situation which has created an image problem for the insurance business.

A company, which fails to settle claims to the satisfaction of customers, would definitely attract less business, as it is likely to discourage such clients to continue to insure with the company. Such customers might advise their family, friends, colleagues, and relations not to patronize such a company.

Prudent claims administration strategy enhances sales and promotes customer loyalty as it helps to develop a perception of "membership" or "belonging" within a particular group of

customers, thereby providing the company with opportunities of retaining existing customers while attracting new ones and profitable one (Braers, 2004).

The consequence of the above problem could lead to a downward trend in sales of insurance (comprehensive motor insurance), low premium income, decrease in insurance contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP) of a country, poor consumer trust and confidence in Nigeria insurance market.

This study will therefore look at the effects of prompt claims settlement on the sales of comprehensive motor insurance.

1.3 RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this study is to investigate the trends in the company's claim settlement system and a thorough review of existing claims handling processes. The company would therefore be advised on the best way to settle claims that would ensure customer satisfaction. This will in turn redeem the image of insurance in the eyes of the insuring public and also improve the sales of insurance products.

The aim of this study is to critically examine the effect of prompt claim settlement on the sales of Comprehensive Motor insurance. Also the study has the following objectives:

- 1 To show the relationship between prompt claims settlement and purchase of insurance.
- 2 To find out if claim settlement period falls within the period prescribed by the law.
- 3 To find out if the company has complaint service unit.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research exercise is set out to ensure, the following questions.

- 1 Does prompt claims settlement have any effect on the sales of Comprehensive motor insurance?
- 2 Does the claims settlement period fall within the period prescribed by the law?
- 3 Does the company have any structure in place to ensure customers satisfaction and to cater for customer complaints?

1.5 SCOPE OF STUDY

The study is based on the Nigeria insurance market. The research will be carried out in Lagos specifically, where most of the insurance companies have their headquarters and also it is a cosmopolitan area. The research will investigate the company's claim service delivery vis-à-vis their customer services and corresponding effects on sales of Comprehensive motor insurance in the companies.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The payments of claims are not only a legal obligation but also a strong public relations instrument and a marketing strategy has a lot of bearing on the sales of insurance products. This study aims at identifying whether claims settlement affect the demand for the company's insurance products and customer choices. This study will help to have a positive effect of improving the image of insurance company in the sub-region and the improved image will, in turn, increase demand for their insurance products and increase premium income generation/sales, capital formation and contribution to the economy of the country in the sub-region.

1.7 LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

A major constraint is the time available for the study research, which is limiting. This therefore will force the researcher to limit the research to just five (5) insurance companies.

Another limiting factor is the few weeks duration allocated to the completion of the research work by the school authorities. This will therefore limit the researcher to carry out a detailed research work.

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CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The history of insurance describes the development of the modern business of insurance against risks, especially regarding cargo, property, death, automobile accidents, and medical treatment. The industry helps to eliminate risks (as when fire insurance companies demand the implementation of safe practices and installation of hydrants), spreads risks from the individual to the larger community, and provides an important source of long-term finance for both the public and private sectors. The insurance industry is generally profitable and provides attractive employment opportunities for white collar workers (www.google.com)

2.2 CLASSIFICATION OF THE INSURANCE BUSINESS

According to section 2 of the Insurance Act May, 2003, there shall be for the purpose of the act, two main classes of insurance business;

1. Life Insurance Business
2. General Insurance Business

The general business is further classified into 8 categories.

- a. Fire insurance business
- b. General accident business
- c. Motor vehicle insurance business
- d. Marine and aviation insurance business
- e. Oil and gas insurance business
- f. Engineering insurance business
- g. Bonds credit guarantee and suretyship insurance business
- h. Miscellaneous insurance business.

2.3 SALES OF INSURANCE SERVICE

(CONCEPT OF SERVICE MARKETING)

Service is an intangible product involving a deed, performance or effort that cannot be physically possessed. Service marketing has been defined as an economic activity that does not result in ownership (Jobber, 2004). Services are unusual type of products, which require extra understanding and efforts to deliver. This is basically due to the fact that services are not as tangible as other physical products. A customer can only derive satisfaction from a service by fulfillment. There is no single commonly accepted definition of the term however, Gabbot and Hogg (1993) as referred to by Manyo-Plange (2004), states that “Services are a series of deeds, processes and performances”. Conventional marketing concepts cannot easily be applied to services because of the characteristics of services, which make them distinctive. More importantly, services cannot be produced in independent processes, that is, processes that are conducted and fully controlled by the service provider. In order to produce a service,

the production process involves the customer, example, the customer must be present when their hair is being cut, and the customer's money is involved when using the services of a bank and the customer's car is involved in a car wash service. Services account for a greater proportion of the economies in developed countries (Kotler, Amstrong, Saunders and Wong, 2001).

2.4 CHARACTERISTICS OF INSURANCE PRODUCTS

2.4.1 INTANGIBILITY: A pure service cannot be assessed using any of the physical senses – it is an abstraction which cannot be directly examined before it is purchased. A prospective purchaser of most goods is able to examine the goods for physical integrity, aesthetic appearance, taste, smell, etc (Palmer,2005).The suggested strategies for problems stemming from intangibility of services include creating and stressing tangible features (Berry 1980), to make the service more conspicuous. Other strategies to overcome intangibility of service include creating a strong organizational image, engaging in post-purchase communication, using cost accounting to set prices (Zeithaml, 1981) and replicating word of mouth communications (Berry, 1980). The level of intangibility has been proposed as a means of distinguishing between products and services (Levitt, 1981). Zeithaml (1981) said further that the level of intangibility has implication for the ease with which consumers can evaluate services and products.

The level of tangibility present in the service offer, according to Palmer (2005) derives from three principal sources:

- Tangible goods, which are includes in the service offer and consumed by the user
- The physical environment in which the service production/consumption process takes place, and
- Tangible evidence of service performance

2.4.2 INSEPARABILITY: The production and consumption of a tangible good are two discrete activities. Production and consumption are said to be separable, on the other hand, the consumption of a service is said to be inseparable from its means of production (Palmer,2005). Palmer (2005) says inseparability occurs whether the producer is human- as in the case of healthcare services or a machine (e.g. a bank ATM machine). The service of the ATM can only be realized if the producer and consumer interact. This notion of inseparability between production and consumption gave rise to the idea of relationship marketing. The salesperson's ability to reduce perceived uncertainty determines relationship quality from the consumer's perspective (Zeithaml, 1981). Researchers in service marketing such as; (Engwall, 1984; Grönroos, 1979; Zeithaml et al.,1985) have thus stressed the significance of buyer-seller interactions and long-term relationships. Copulsky and Wolf, (1990) therefore defined relationship marketing as “an organization's effort to develop a long-term, cost effective link with individual customers for mutual benefit”.

2.4.3 HETEROGENEITY: It is very difficult to make each service experience identical. For instance, a concert performed by a group on two nights may differ in slight ways because it is very difficult to standardize every dance move. Generally, systems and procedures are put into place to make sure the service provided is consistent all the time, training in service

organizations is essential for this, however in saying this there will always be delicate differences because a service is produced and consumed simultaneously, and because individual people make up part of the service offering, it can be argued that a service is always unique; it only exists once, and is never exactly repeated. This can give rise to concern about service quality and uniformity issues. Personnel training and careful monitoring of customer satisfaction and feedback can help to maintain high standards. This is a particular difficulty for services with high labor content, as different people deliver the service performance and the performance of people can vary from day to day (Rathmell, 1966). Onkvisit and Shaw (1991) consider heterogeneity to offer the opportunity to provide a degree of flexibility and customization of the service. Wyckham, R.G, Fitzroy, P. and Mandry, G. (1975) suggest that heterogeneity can be introduced as a benefit and point of differentiation.

2.4.4 PERISHABILITY: In general, services cannot be stored and because of this time constraint consumers demand more. Services are perishable; they cannot be stored and carried forward to a future time period (Rathmell, 1966). Onkvisit and Shaw (1991) suggest that services are “time dependent” and “time important” which make them very perishable. Therefore an empty seat on a plane, for example, is a lost opportunity forever. Restaurants are now charging for reservations, which are not kept, charges may be made for missed appointments at the dental clinic. Hartman and Lindgren, (1993) says that “issue of perishability is primarily the concern of the service producer” and that the consumer only becomes aware of the issue when there is insufficient supply and they have to wait for the service. Perishability does not pose too much of a problem when demand for a service is steady, but in times of unusually high or low demand service organizations can have severe difficulties. Conversely, during periods of low demand, the service firm may encourage trial of its products or services through promotions, add new and innovative services, make the working hours and location more convenient and even offer price promotions.

2.5 MANAGING SERVICE QUALITY

A service provider can principally distinguish itself from its competitors by improving service quality, which will eventually increase customer satisfaction leading to sales and profits. “In the UK, local councils are facing increasing pressure to deliver higher quality services to the local communities they serve.”(Jobber, 2004) Exceptional quality services which will pay-off must aim at greater customer satisfaction, which will lead to increased retention and sales To meet quality targets, the service providers need to identify the expectations of target customers concerning service quality. Jobber (2004) argues that most companies have been eluded on the issue of high standard of service quality because of the four causes of poor perceived quality. He further says that these barriers separate the perception of service quality from what customers expect, and to manage services well, they must be overcome. These four causes are; Misconception barrier talks about the disparity in understanding from management and what the customer expects. This can only be resolved by marketing research. Inadequate resources barrier highlights on the fact that managers may

understand what customers expect but might be unwilling to provide the resources to meet that because of cost reduction policies. Inadequate delivery barrier positions the manager understands of what the customers expect and provide adequate resources to meet that but fail to select, train and reward staff adequately resulting in poor and inconsistent service. Exaggerated promises barrier emphasizes that even though all the above barriers are overcome, a gap between customer expectation and perceptions still remain through exaggerated promises.

2.5.2 CHALLENGES OF SERVICE MAKETING

There are lots of challenges facing the insurer in the selling of his products (Chilekezi, 2006)

Challenges of service marketing as stipulated by Schultz and Doerr (2008), below are some of the most common and difficult challenges of growing and managing consulting, professional, or technology service businesses that don't necessary apply to product businesses.

1. Clients cannot see or touch services before they purchase them. This makes services difficult to conceptualize and evaluate from the client perspective, creating increased uncertainty and perception of risk. From the firm's perspective, service intangibility can make services difficult to promote, control quality, and set price.
2. Services are often produced and consumed simultaneously. This creates special challenges in service quality management that product companies do not even consider. Unlike service, products are tested before they go out the door but service production happens with the customer present, creating a very different and challenging dynamic
3. Trust is necessary. Some level of trust in the service organization and its people must be established before clients will engage services.
4. Competition is often not who you think. Competitions for product companies are other product companies. Competitions for service companies are often the clients themselves. Sometimes you find yourself in a competitive shootout (some firms more than others), but often the client is asking „should we engage this service at all“?
5. Service deliverers often do the selling. Many product companies have dedicated sales forces. For services, the selling is often split between sales, marketing, professional, and management staff.
6. Marketing and sales lose momentum. Most product companies have dedicated marketers and sellers. They market and sell continuously, regardless of the revenue levels they generate. In many services companies the marketers and sellers also must manage and deliver. This can often lead to the wide swings between revenue and extra work, and revenue and work deficiency.
7. Passion is necessary, yet elusive. The more passion, spirit, hustle, and desire your staff brings to the organization every day, the more revenue and success you will have. The

correlation between staff passion and financial success is direct and measurable (as is the correlation between lack-of-passion and organizational failure).

2.6 OVERVIEW OF CLAIMS IN INSURANCE

Claims are evolving in Europe. The Chartered Insurance Institute Claims faculty reports, "over recent years there have been many changes to the way in which claims are handled, viewed and managed. These changes are incremental and accumulative, rather than sudden and dramatic and this has created an ever-changing and evolving claims environment. It is agreed that claims is much closer to the heart of the industry than ever before and in many cases is believed to be the biggest trigger to an organizations profits and loss. So it is not surprising that in this ever-competitive industry, a claim has a greater presence. (Claims Faculty, CII 2007).

The concept of insurance services is not a new phenomenon to the citizens of Nigeria. This is because of the nature of the extended family unit and communal practices in the areas. For instance, an individual or group in the community may suffer loss either through theft, flood disaster, farm destruction by pest or flood, fire disaster, death, accident, or any form of loss. The immediate extended family and or some members of the community who are friends or neighbors will quickly come to sympathize and support the person by way of gifts and personal donations. In order to help reduce the suffering, which is restoring or putting back the insured to the position he was before suffering a loss. This role was gradually taken over by insurance industry in our modern society (Garba and Abdulsalam, 2011). This action could better be described as a traditional way of indemnity, which is restoring or putting back the insured in the position he was before suffering a loss. This role was gradually taken over by insurance industry in our modern society. Different types of claims, such as first-party auto physical damage, first-party property, liability, and worker's compensation claims, require different treatment from the claim representative to be properly investigated and paid. Despite these differences, claim representatives can perform the same basic activities to handle any type of claim (Pamela, Donna, and Doris, 2005). These claims handling activities are;

- i. Acknowledging and assigning the claim.
- ii. Identifying the policy.
- iii. Contacting the insured or the insured's representative.
- iv. Investigating and documenting the claim.
- v. Determining the cause of loss and the loss amount.
- vi. Concluding the claim.

2.6.2 CLAIMS SETTLEMENT PROCEDURE

According to Iruku, (1977), it may be pertinent to identify the underlying claim settlement procedure involved as follows:

- i. **Notification:** All insurance policies require notification in writing “immediately” or “as soon as practicable” after a loss has occurred. Notification may be made through an agent or broker or directly to the insurance company. Some policies stipulate that the notice must be sent to the insurers within a specified number of days. Failure to give the notice within the stipulated number of days is a breach of the terms of the policy, which might entitle the insurer to repudiate liability.
- ii. **Verification:** Verification of records is to ensure that there was cover at the time of the loss against the peril that caused the loss. This involves an examination of records in the insurer’s office to ascertain that the relevant policy was in force at that material time and that the policy covers the event that led to the loss.
- iii. **Proof of Loss:** The onus is on the insured to prove his loss. The claimant has to convince the Insurer not only that a loss has occurred, but that the loss was caused by an insured peril. If the Insured fails to prove their loss, the claim may fail. The policyholder must also prove the quantum or the extent of their loss.
- iv. **Negotiation:** Most claims are settled by means of negotiation between the parties without the need for such formal procedures as arbitration or litigation. This is, of course, the fastest and most economical method of adjustment. In most claims, there may be nothing over which to negotiate and the claim may be paid almost immediately. When negotiation does not work out, the contract may itself prescribe some other procedure to be followed, such as arbitration and litigation.
 - a. **Arbitration:** Where negotiations break down or fail to achieve the desired objectives, the other option available is Arbitration. It is the settlement of a dispute by the decision of one or more persons called Arbitrators. The decision of an Arbitrator is called an Award and it can be enforced by legal process in the same way the judgment of a law court could be enforced.
 - b. **Litigation:** is another method of settling insurance dispute where the aggrieved party goes to the law court to seek redress. This option is chosen where Negotiation and Arbitration fails. In practice, insurers are reluctant in going to court so as to protect their image. In most cases, insurers always strive to get problems solved before it gets out of hand or resort to litigation.
- v. **Payment of Claims:** When all activities associated with adjustment of the loss are completed and the amount of loss is determined and agreed upon, the insured is entitled to receive payment. There are at least four methods of payment, which insurers can employ in providing claim settlements. They are as follows:
 - Cash Payments
 - Repair
 - Replacement
 - Reinstatement

The option as to which method is to be employed is normally given to the insured by wording of the policy. In spite of the above, the insurer, in paying claims must

balance the interest of the claimant and all other policyholders who have contributed to the fund. Although the claimant is entitled to be paid in accordance with the promise of the insurance contract, the fund should be protected against payment of unearned claims. There are certain prohibiting factors like Average and Excess/franchise/deductibles inherent in the practice of the insurance that makes it possible for clients not to receive their full payment. Average is a condition in the policy which provides that where the amount of premium paid by the insured is only for a smaller proportion of the total value at risk, since that is what has been disclosed by the insured, any claims settlement under this policy will recognize this fact and the amount payable to the insured will be proportionately reduced.

- vi. **Excess/Franchise/Deductibles** are amounts of money (decided at inception of the policy) that are subtracted from each claim to be settled. It is immediately observed that should the total amount of the claim be less than the amount of the excess/franchise/deductibles the claim will not be paid (Wildman, et al, 2005).
- vii. **Ex-gratia** occurs when a client suffers a loss or incurs some liability for which the insurer cannot be held liable, under the policy. This client may be a valued client to the insurer and the insurer may want to identify with him during his misfortune. In such situations the practice of insurance allow for the payment “out of grace” (ex-gratia) of monies to the insured. Therefore, this is a claim payment made by the insurer out of favor even though there is no legal obligation (Chiejina, 2004).

2.6.3 CONDITIONS THAT CAN INHIBIT CLAIMS SETTLEMENT

There are some policy conditions that can constrain the insurer in the payment of full amount due (indemnity). These are:

- a. **Sum insured:** The limit of liability for an insurer is the sum insured. If the sum insured is less than the loss incurred, the insurer will only settle up to the sum insured.
- b. **Excess or franchise:** Excess is a policy condition in which an insured is made to bear a certain amount in every claim presented, e.g. the first #5,000 in every loss. Franchise, on the other hand, is where the insured is made to bear all the losses if the claim is lower than a certain fixed amount. The insurer would pay the cost of all claims when the cost exceeds the specified amount (Isimoya, 2007). Aduloju (2009) says excess is the first part of each and every claim, which is borne by insured, and this reduces indemnity being paid.
- c. **Limit per article:** This is where the policy condition specifies the maximum amount to be paid per article in the event of a loss. The implication is that any article whose value the insured considers to be higher than the specified amount should be insured specifically.
- d. **Operation of average:** This is a term used to ensure that losses are paid in direct proportion to the degree of underinsurance. Thus, if a commercial warehouse is insured for 30% less than the value or risk (the sum insured is 70% of value of warehouse), the insurer would only pay 70% in the event of any loss (Isimoya, 2007).

2.6.4 CLAIMS DISPUTES

Disputes arise in claims between the insured and the insurer involving:

- i. Whether the insurer is liable or not, e.g. if the claimant is a third party, the insurer may insist that the insured (therefore they) have no liability at all.
- ii. The amount payable in that liability (quantum) (Isimoya, 2007).

2.6.5 WAYS OF RESOLVING CLAIMS DISPUTES

When such disagreements arise, the claim officials have the following options to reach a settlement; Negotiation, Arbitration, Litigation.

Negotiation: A disagreement may be settled by discussion between the parties involved, without the need for such judicial procedures arbitration, litigation etc. In negotiation, which is the most economical and fastest means of claims' adjustment, one party's point of view will prevail or an amicable compromise is reached. In property insurance, where an amount of loss may be difficult to ascertain, negotiation could be used. In life, the amount payable is certain and so no negotiation.

Arbitration: This is where an independent person not involved in the dispute is appointed by both disputing parties to decide on the case. Most property contracts contain an arbitration condition. This condition rests the rights of both parties to go to a law court in case of dispute.

Litigation: This may be the last resort for the determination of the amount payable in a dispute of claims. If the dispute cannot be resolved by discussions by both parties and the amount involved is large, court proceedings may become necessary (Isimoya, 2007).

2.7 CLAIMS ADMINISTRATION AND E-COMMERCE

The utilization of new and better technology, better business process and off shoring have all been contributing factors in the evolution of claims. The much reported but none-the-less outstanding emergence of the Internet is playing a major part in enabling reduction in cost and expenses and more innovative and responsive customer service. For example, on-line claims tracking and rapid communications through standardized formats for requesting for information enables insurers to differentiate their brand from their competitors and to provide a better service to their customers. (Collins,1997). Claims processing is designed to allow claims to be recorded within the insurer's records and for a reserve to be set up for the potential liabilities involved in the claims as quickly and as smoothly as possible. A function, which for many years was a purely manual, one or one, which had the assistance of certain accounting machines, has now been taken over to a large extent by computers. The reliance of technology has been given a great boost by the coming into being of technology where there is reliance of telephone and the necessity for giving of service which is both quick and efficient, is of prime importance. (Collins,1997). The e-business revolution is gaining committed converts among increasing numbers of insurance companies and brokers world over. According to Bruis, (2000), a research conducted on over 60 leading insurance and financial organizations in, the UK identified that a staggering 90% of processing today in commercial insurance remains paper based. The subsequent cost of this with other expenses

amounted to as much as 35% of the net premium, in the main, due to duplication of administration between parties.

2.8 INSURANCE CLAIMS FRAUD

Insurance fraud remains an issue, but even though it is becoming more effective at detecting the cheats, this is not an image it wants to project.

The Association of British Insurers report, June 2003, estimates such fraud costs in the insurance industry to be in excess of £1 billion per year. The report states that insurance fraud arises not only when individuals make false claim for an accident\event that has not occurred, but also when individuals inflate claims for genuine incidents. This highlights the importance of putting in place effective strategies to detect fraud but also raises some interesting issues around prevention. (Stears, 2003).Below are facts and figures of the official view of costs and impacts of fraud crime as quoted by the Tenth Annual Review Report (2007-2008) of the Fraud Advisory Panel-UK;"Financial crime costs at least £13.9 billion, increasing to £20 billion when income tax and EU related fraud are taken into account. This amounts to £330 for every man; woman and child in the UK. Individuals lost at least £2.75 billion whereas businesses lost £3.7 billion in 2005.The public sector was defrauded at least £6.8 billion in 2005-2006." (Association of Police Officers, March 2007)."Fraud is a hidden tax on everyone. It increases the cost of goods and services, impoverishes small as well as corporate shareholders, strikes at the future of private pension holders, and jeopardizes jobs and saps faith in the country's unique standing at home and abroad. It damages business growth and investment'. (Fraud Review, June 2006)"In monetary terms the harm [fraud] causes is on a par with Class A drugs" {Lord Goldsmith QC (February, 2007)}.

The leadership of fraud-dominated countries describes trans-national organized crime and fraud as a threat to national security, which reflects in the statement from the cabinet office below;"The potential effects include: undermining legitimate cross-border trade; threatening the integrity of financial markets through large scale money-laundering; and threatening business and individuals through cyber-crime."(National Security Strategy of the United Kingdom Cabinet Office, March 2008).

Although insurance Companies are joining with other bodies to launch a major crackdown on fraudulent insurance proposals and claims such as false theft reports, staged accidents, arson claims for personal profit, multiple claims on same property and material falsehood at the proposal stage. Needless to say, sometimes even the most honest claims may have been refused their compensation because of difficulty in telling whether the claim was genuine.

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CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 PREAMBLE

According to Asika (2004), Research Methodology should provide a detailed account used in collection of data, why those methods were chosen and not others, what data were obtained and how they were obtained.

This chapter shows the technique used in collecting and gathering data for this project, which describe the population of study, the sampling procedure used and the limitation to the methodology. It also specifies the sample size adopted and the data collection instrument used for the project with method adopted to analyze the data gathered.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is the strategy, the plan, and the structure of conducting a research project (Micheal, 2000). The survey research design was used in the course of study.

3.2 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Population is the number of items from which to draw a sample (Statistical & Technical Team, 1999). Due to the nature of this study are in two sets of population. The first set of the population is the insuring public, who may have cause to purchase motor insurance, while the second set of the population consist of all employees of insurance companies underwriting motor policies in Nigeria. One of the bases for choosing this population location for the study was because Lagos is a cosmopolitan area in which we have people from different tribe, culture, ethnic, sociological and educational background and also the insurance companies have their headquarters in Lagos as well as most of the activities within the industry take place in Lagos.

3.3 SAMPLING PROCEDURE AND SAMPLE SIZE

In view of what was said about the population study as regards time frame and cost, a sampling procedure will be chosen. Section of sampling procedure to be adopted was contingent on the practical and theoretical sense which includes the purpose, nature and time frame of the study. However, random sampling would be used because of the ease of usage, and its unbiased nature because it is representative in nature. According to information gathered from NAICOM, there are about 57 government approved and duly registered insurance companies operating in Nigeria, in which 30 transact non-life business, 16 transact life business and 11 are composite. 41(30 non life and 11 composite) was the major population of this study. A minimum of 12 per cent of those insurance companies were presented with 50 questionnaires. The questionnaires were administered to at least ten randomly chosen insurance companies to get a wider range of data and opinion on claims settlement and number of policies.

The 5 sample insurance companies are as follows;

Custodian and allied insurance plc

Goldlink insurance plc

Staco insurance plc

Law union and rock insurance plc

Sterling assurance plc

3.4 DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

The main instrument used for the collection of relevant data was questionnaire since it is the primary method of data collection; also secondary data was collected from the selected insurance companies for analysis and comparison of results from the questionnaire used. The questionnaire was constructed in two sections, sections A and B, and for two respondents as well, company's staffs and the public. Section A requested for the respondents' sex, age group, marital status, working years experience, educational background, work position, while section B of both questionnaires requested for the respondents opinion on the relevant variables of the research questions.

3.5 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

After the collection of data from respondents through questionnaire, both qualitative and quantitative descriptive method was used to summarize collected data using an analytical tool, statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), analysis output included; descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

3.6 LIMITATION OF THE METHODOLOGY

The study was limited in terms of respondents that will be used because if a larger number is used, a different conclusion will be derived. Also, substantial amount of effort was put into the designing of the research work and administration of questionnaire, certain problems were encountered which are worth mentioning. Some of the limitations include;

Some of the respondents were illiterates and who are not aware of insurance business. The time frame of the study was limiting because if a longer time was given, there might be a different result.

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CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, the responses from claimants were categorized according to sex, age, educational background and marital status. This was followed by the presentation and analysis of data according to the research questions. The data are presented using cross tabulations.

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: PRESENTATION OF DEMOGRAPHICAL DATA OF RESPONDENT

		age of respondents	marital status of respondents	educational background of respondents	sex of respondent
N	Valid	124	124	124	150
	Missing	26	26	26	0

Field survey: 2014

Table 1 indicates that out of the 150 questionnaires administered to the Insuring public, a total of 124 were completed and returned and 24 was missing.

Table 2: Sex of respondent

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
missing	26	17.3	17.3	17.3
Valid	Male	71	47.3	64.7
	female	53	35.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Field survey: 2014

The table shows that a large proportion of respondent were male representing 47.3% and the female constituting 35.3%, 17.3% represents the proportion of data that was missing.

Table 3: Age of respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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	18-30	32	21.3	25.8	25.8
	31-40	43	28.7	34.7	60.5
Valid	41-50	23	15.3	18.5	79.0
	51-60	17	11.3	13.7	92.7
	above 60	9	6.0	7.3	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

Table 3 shows that out of the respondents, 25.8% of respondents were within the 18-30 years age bracket, 34.7% of respondents were within the 31-40 years age bracket, 18.5% of respondents were within 41-50, also 13.7% of respondents were within the 51-60 years age bracket and 7.3% were above 60 years.

Table 4

Marital status of respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Married	75	50.0	60.5	60.5
Valid	Single	49	32.7	39.5	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

Table 4 shows that out of the respondents 60.5% were married, 39.5% were single.

Table 5

Educational background of respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Primary	7	4.7	5.6	5.6

secondary	16	10.7	12.9	18.5
Tertiary	47	31.3	37.9	56.5
professional	54	36.0	43.5	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The educational background of the respondents, which is represented by Table 5, shows that 7(5.6%) of the respondents were primary school leavers, 16(12.9) % valid respondents were secondary school leavers, 47(37.9%) valid respondents had completed tertiary education and 54(43.5%) were professionals.

4.3 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONS

Table 1: Do you have motor insurance policy?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	103	68.7	83.1	83.1
Valid No	21	14.0	16.9	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Table 1 shows the number of policies own by the valid respondent. 83.1% of them indicated yes while 16.9% said no. Majority of the respondent have motor insurance policy.

Table 2: Type of policy?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9

third party fire and theft	15	10.0	12.1	29.0
third party only	37	24.7	29.8	58.9
comprehensive	51	34.0	41.1	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

Table 2 shows the number of the valid respondents' type of policies. Third party fire and theft accounts for 12,1%, third party only is 29,8%, while comprehensive accounts for 41% of the total valid. The table indicates that majority of them own comprehensive motor insurance. Invalid 16.9% ie those not filled as a result of NO.

Table 3 For how long have you had the policy (ies)?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
less than two years	12	8.0	9.7	26.6
Valid 2-5 years	49	32.7	39.5	66.1
6-9 years	24	16.0	19.4	85.5
above 9 years	18	12.0	14.5	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

The table here shows that out of the total valid respondent, 39.5% accounts for 2-5years, while 19.4% accounts for 6-9years, above 9 years account for 14.5% while those invalid is 16.9%. It therefore shows that majority have had their policy for the past 2-5 years.

Table 4 How did you get to know about insurance?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid Friends relations agent/broker	12	8.0	9.7	26.6
	16	10.7	12.9	39.5
	62	41.3	50.0	89.5
Media	13	8.7	10.5	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

This shows how the respondent get to know insurance. The following percentage are 16.9%/9.7%,12.9%, 50% and 10.5% for the following respectively, invalid, friends, relations, agent and broker, and media respectively. Most of them knew through the agent and broker.

Table 5 Do you have friends/relatives currently insured?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid Yes	88	58.7	71.0	87.9
No	15	10.0	12.1	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

The table above basically shows the total number that have their relatives and friend insured. Majorities have their friends and relatives insured ie 71% of the valid respondent while 12.1% said no and invalid accounts for 16.9%.

Table 6 Have you ever made any claim on your insurance policy?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	57	38.0	46.0	62.9
	No	46	30.7	37.1	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

The analysis of the table shows those that have made claims out of the 103 valid respondent. 46% of them have made claims, those who haven't made is 37.1% those who are invalid are 16.9%. majority had made claims on their policies.

Table 7 Was the claim settled by the insurance company?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	52	34.7	41.9	58.9
	No	51	34.0	41.1	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

Here, shows the percent of those 46% that have made claim in the previous question. And have been settled is 41.9% while those not settled amounts to 41.1% leaving the invalid with 16.9%. conclusively, majority had been settled.

Table 8 How long did it take the insurance company to settle the claim?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9

	within 1 week	1	.7	.8	17.7
	2 weeks	3	2.0	2.4	20.2
	3-4 weeks	23	15.3	18.5	38.7
	5-6 weeks	7	4.7	5.6	44.4
	6-8 weeks	8	5.3	6.5	50.8
	9-12 weeks	6	4.0	4.8	55.6
	above weeks	12 55	36.7	44.4	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System		26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

Having been settled, the number of the valid respondent that were settled within 3 months is while those that were settled outside three months are 44.4% while the invalid amounts to 16.9% leaving those settled within the time frame of the three months to be 39.7%. this shows that most are not settled within the prescribed time.

Table 9 How long did you expect the settlement to take?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
	within 1 week	1	.7	.8	17.7
	2 weeks	31	20.7	25.0	42.7
	3-4 weeks	36	24.0	29.0	71.8
Valid	5-6 weeks	8	5.3	6.5	78.2
	6-8 weeks	5	3.3	4.0	82.3
	9-12 weeks	4	2.7	3.2	85.5
	above weeks	12 18	12.0	14.5	100.0

Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The table above indicates the expectation of the valid respondent. those who expect the settlement to take place within the 3months is while expectation of some of them is 14.5%. that falls outside the 3 months time frame. The invalid accounts for16.9% out of the total valid respondent. This shows that their expectation are to some degree been met.

Table 10 Was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
no	27	18.0	21.8	38.7
Valid yes	41	27.3	33.1	71.8
indifferent	35	23.3	28.2	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The table shows the number of people whose claims equaled the payment. evidently ,majority of the respondent opined that they were satisfied with the payment by 33.1% while NO accounts for21.8%, indifferent is 28.2% and those that are invalid is 16.9%.

Table 11 To what extent were you satisfied with the claim amount paid?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
not satisfied	36	24.0	29.0	46.0

	Satisfied	8	5.3	6.5	52.4
	very satisfied	23	15.3	18.5	71.0
	indifferent	36	24.0	29.0	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The table above shows the degree of satisfaction of the claim amount paid. the conclusion that could be arrived at is that majority of the respondent are not satisfied with 29% while 6.5% are satisfied, 18.5% are very satisfied, 29% are indifferent leaving 16.9% to be invalid.

Table 12 To what extent were you satisfied with the length of time taken to settle the claim?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
not satisfied	55	36.7	44.4	61.3
satisfied	25	16.7	20.2	81.5
Valid very satisfied	3	2.0	2.4	83.9
indifferent	20	13.3	16.1	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3	
Total	150	100.0		

From the above, it is evident that 44.4% of the valid respondent that responded said they were not satisfied which accounts for majority of the respondent. From the above 20.2 % were satisfied, 2.4% were very satisfied while 16.1% were indifferent and 16.1% of the respondent were invalid.

Table 13 How would you describe the claims handling procedure of the company?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
satisfactory	27	18.0	21.8	38.7
very satisfactory	4	2.7	3.2	41.9
poor	45	30.0	36.3	78.2
very poor	27	18.0	21.8	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

This table addresses the attitude of the respondent as regards the claim handling process of the company. accordingly, most respondent regarded the handling procedure of the company to be poor with the percentage of 36.3% with the highest. 21.8%, 3.2%, and 21.8% are the percent for the following respectively, satisfactory, very satisfactory and very poor. The percent for invalid is 16.9%.

Table 14 Has the insurance company ever declined your claim at any time?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Yes	69	46.0	55.6	72.6

No	34	22.7	27.4	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The above table exhibit the number of respondent that their claim were declined which is 55.6%. indicated that there claim were declined while those who said no were 27.4%, the remaining percent is 16.9% for invalid.

Table 15 Were you given any reason by the company as to why you claim was declined?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid Yes	58	38.7	46.8	63.7
Valid No	45	30.0	36.3	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

The table exhibits the respondent that were given reasons for decline and those not given. 46.8% indicated that they were given reasons for the decline while 36.3% said they were not given reasons. The percent for invalid is 16.9%. However it could be deduced that those not probably were no well informed about the reason.

Table 16 What were the reasons given?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid breach of policy condition	11	7.3	8.9	25.8

loss not covered by policy	24	16.0	19.4	45.2
lack of insurable interest	33	22.0	26.6	71.8
delay in notification	35	23.3	28.2	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The above table shows the various reasons for the decline of claim submitted by those who indicated that their claim was declined. Apparently, most of the cause of decline was from delay in notification (28.2%) while 16.9%, 8.9%, 19.4%, 26.6% accounts for invalid, breach of policy condition, loss not covered by policy and lack of insurable interest respectively.

Table 17 were you satisfied by the reason given for the decline of your claim?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid				
Yes	55	36.7	44.4	61.3
No	48	32.0	38.7	100.0
Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing System	26	17.3		
Total	150	100.0		

The table shows the satisfaction of those respondents that their claims were declined. 44.4% of the valid respondent was satisfied by the reasons given to them and this accounted for majority of the respondent. 38.7% were not satisfied .16.9% were invalid.

Table 18 Did you have any complaints service unit to lodge your complaints or appeal?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	yes	67	44.7	54.0	71.0
	no	36	24.0	29.0	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Field survey: 2014

The following percent represents the response of the respondent as regards having a complaint unit to lodge appeal. 54% of the respondent indicated that they have a complaint unit to lodge their complaint and appeal while 29% of the valid respondent said they don't have a complaint unit to complain or lodge their appeal. 16.9% accounts for invalid percent

Table 19 Will you continue to maintain your policy in spite of your claim being declined?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	50	33.3	40.3	57.3
	No	53	35.3	42.7	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

From the above, it can be deduced that lesser degree of the respondent opined that they would still continue to maintain their policy even when their claim was declined as this was represented by 40.3% while greater percent indicated that they would not maintain their policy as their claim was declined accounts for 42.7%. However, the percent for invalid is 16.9%. From the foregoing, it can be deduced that declination of claim has an immense effect.

Table 20 Do you intend to buy some other insurance policy(ies) from the company?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	57	38.0	46.0	62.9
	No	46	30.7	37.1	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

This shows the percent of those who still want to or intend to buy another policy. Majority of the respondent would still want to buy more policy while those say NO is 37.1%. however the percent of invalid is 16.9%.

Table 21 Would you recommend others to insure with the company given your experience?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	63	42.0	50.8	67.7
	No	40	26.7	32.3	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

This table indicate the percent of those that would recommend insurance given their experience in which most of the valid respondent ie 50.8% for yes would recommend as against those who would not recommend which is 30.3. the total number of invalid is 16.9%.

Table 22 Have you being paying insurance premium without making a claim on your policy?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	57	38.0	46.0	62.9
	No	46	30.7	37.1	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

Accordingly, most of the valid respondent have been paying premium without making a claim through the 46% indicating yes while that of NO is 37.1% have not been paying premium without making claims. The percent of the invalid is the constant 16.9%.

Table 23 Will you continue to maintain your policy even when you have not been making claim?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Invalid	21	14.0	16.9	16.9
Valid	Yes	66	44.0	53.2	70.2
	No	37	24.7	29.8	100.0
	Total	124	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	26	17.3		
Total		150	100.0		

The table above shows that 53.2% of the number that have not made any claim while 29.8% shows that they would not maintain their policy if they don't make claims. This elicit that most of the respondent would still maintain their policy even without making claim.

4.4 ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH QUESTIONS

4.4.1 RESEARCH QUESTION 1

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
to what extent were you satisfied with the claim amount paid? * was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?	124	82.7%	26	17.3%	150	100.0%
would you recommend others to insure with the company given your experience? * was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?	124	82.7%	26	17.3%	150	100.0%
do you intend to buy some other insurance policy(ies) * was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?	124	82.7%	26	17.3%	150	100.0%

Field survey: 2014

to what extent were you satisfied with the claim amount paid? / was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you? Cross tabulation

		was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?		
		invalid	no	yes
to what extent were you satisfied with the claim amount paid?	Invalid	21	0	0
	not satisfied	0	27	9
	satisfied	0	0	8

	very satisfied	0	0	23
	indifferent	0	0	1
Total		21	27	41

Table shows that 41 of the valid respondents said the claim settlement amount paid to them was equal to the expected estimates submitted to the insurance company whereas 27 valid respondents said the amount paid was not equal to the expected claim submitted to the insurance company. The higher figure recorded for those respondents who expected more amounts than they received may be attributable to excesses/deductibles imposed or adjustment made by claims officers to validate the estimates presented and dismiss any fraudulent presentations.

Out of these numbers, 31 valid respondents stated that they were satisfied and very with the claim settlement amount paid to them whilst 93 valid respondents stated that they were dissatisfied and indifferent and never made claim with the amount paid to them. The frequency of respondents who did not receive the amount they expected and were not satisfied, may be an indication that the amount received as effect on the satisfaction customers derive from the claims settlement. From the table 21 respondents had never made a claim nor had their claims declined.

Would you recommend others to insure with the company given your experience? / was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you? Crosstabulation

		was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?			
		invalid	No	Yes	indifferent
would you recommend others to insure with the company given your experience?	invalid	21	0	0	0
	yes	0	27	36	0
	no	0	0	5	35
Total		21	27	41	35

Table above shows that although 40 out of 124 valid respondents stated that the amount paid was not equal to the sum claimed, only 27 of them indicated that they would recommend insurance to others.

Responses related to Table above shows there is enough evidence to suggest that the amount paid has effect on the readiness of the insured to recommend insurance to others. Accordingly, the amount paid has an effect on the insured's readiness to recommend insurance to others. As evidenced by the results in the table, any claimant who responded positive or negative to questions in table would you intend and claims submitted equal to payment, responded the same to this question and the reasons for that were the same.

Based on the analyses of the **Responses related to Table above** it can be concluded that non-payment of the insured's expected claim amount has effect on the sales and marketing of insurance products, thus on re-purchase of the same product or recommendation by word of mouth to prospective insured'

Do you intend to buy some other insurance policy(ies) * was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you? Cross tabulation

		Was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you?			
		invalid	No	Yes	Indifferent
do you intend to buy some other insurance policy(ies)	Invalid	21	0	0	0
	Yes	0	27	30	0
	No	0	0	11	35
Total		21	27	41	35

Table 4.8 above shows that although 27 out of 124 valid respondents stated that the amount

paid was not equal to the sum claimed, none of them indicated that they will not take another policy. Note that 21 of the valid respondents either did not submit any claim nor had their claims declined. From this data, it is evident that, about 18 of claimants who were not satisfied with the amount paid to them would not want to take another policy with the same insurance company. Nonetheless, there could be other claimants who would want to still insure with the same company because of customer loyalty or have close ties with the company or staff of the company.

4.4.2 RESEARCH QUESTION 2

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
how long did it take the insurance company to settle the claim? * how long did you expect	124	82.7%	26	17.3%	150	100.0%

How long did it take the insurance company to settle the claim? / How long did you expect the claim settlement take?

		how long did you expect			Total
		invalid	less than 12 weeks	above 12 weeks	
how long did it take the insurance company to settle the claim?	Invalid	21	0	0	21
	less than 12 weeks	0	48	0	48
	above 12 weeks	0	37	18	55
Total		21	85	18	124

This cross- table shows the relationship between the expectation of the respondent and the actual time taken by the company to settle claims.

48() of the valid respondent expectation about duration of claim settlement were met with the actual time taken to settle the claim. This shows that majority' expectation were met. However there was still a lag in the expectation and actual time of settlement as the rest percent expectation was cut short. However, 21() of the respondent did not answer.

4.4.3 RESEARCH QUESTION 3

The table shows the responses received from the staff of Enterprise Insurance Company to questions relating to structures put in place to cater for claimant's complaints, feedback and on-going customer satisfaction.

	Cases
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	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Managerial level * do you have any complaints service unit where claimants can lodge complaints?	37	74.0%	13	26.0%	50	100.0%
managerial level * do you have any system of customer feedback after claims settlements?	37	74.0%	13	26.0%	50	100.0%
Managerial level * do you undertake on-going claims satisfaction research?	37	74.0%	13	26.0%	50	100.0%

managerial level / do you have any complaints service unit where claimants can lodge complaints? Crosstabulation

	do you have any complaints service unit where claimants can lodge complaints?		Total
	yes	No	
manager	5	0	5
managerial level assistant manager	10	0	10
claims personnel	5	17	22
Total	20	17	37

The results indicate as follows: 20(54.01%) of the valid respondents said there is the existence of a Customer Service Units where claimants could lodge their complaints. therefore most of them affirmed that there was customer unit to lodge there complaint.

Managerial level / do you have any system of customer feedback after claims settlements? Cross tabulation

		do you have any system of customer feedback after claims settlements?		Total
		yes	No	
managerial level	manager	5	0	5
	assistant manager	10	0	10
	claims personnel	0	22	22
Total		15	22	37

Field survey: 2014

In the same vein,15 (40.1%) of the same respondents indicated that they have in place systems for customer feedback after claims settlement. this indicate that majority of the insurance company had a customer feed back. How ever there is still need to improve their quality of service.

managerial level * do you undertake on-going claims satisfaction research? Cross tabulation

		do you undertake on-going claims satisfaction research?		Total
		Yes	No	
managerial level	manager	5	0	5
	assistant manager	7	3	10
	claims personnel	0	22	22
Total		12	25	37

In the table above there was evidence that there was ongoing research for claims satisfaction as most opined that 12(32.4%) stated that there is an on-going customer satisfaction research.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.0 INTRODUCTION

This research was carried out to ascertain “the effect of prompt claim settlement on sales of comprehensive motor insurance policies in Nigeria”.

Claims management, is one of the most valuable possessions of any insurer. It is one aspect of insurance practice, the handling, which can make or mar the image of Insurance Company. In fact, one of the principal functions of Insurance is the settlement of claims because it is the fear that a loss might occur that induces individuals and economic institutions to take out Insurance policies.

The problem of running an effective claims administration that would satisfy the customers, thereby earning the confidence of the customers and consequently inducing repurchase.

Therefore, there was a need to carry out a research to finding out the relationship between prompt claims settlement and purchase of insurance, to find out if claim settlement period falls within the period prescribed by the law, and to find out if the company has complaint service unit.

The emphasis here was to investigate the relationship between fast claims settlement and the sales of insurance products.

Due to the constraints of time, the inability to measure the level of demand using the total sales and marketing figures of the selected company and the fact that the total amount of Claims settled as reflected on their financial statements is not a true reflection of the extent of customer satisfaction in the claims service provided by the insurers, the researcher relied more heavily on the responses from the insuring public.

In order to chart a trend of thought for the research effort, there was the need to have a good understanding of the history of claims and insurance.

There was also the need to review the current literature on service marketing and claims administration to enable the researcher see how other researchers who worked on similar problems went about their study. Some of the important current issues reviewed included the unique features of service marketing, challenges of service marketing, on-line claims tracking and rapid communications, automated claims processing that eliminates lengthy delays, reduces cost, and claims services outsourcing.

The efficient and effective conduct of the entire research work required a description of the approaches used in the study. This was by carrying out a description of the research design, the identification of the data gathering techniques and data processing methods to be adopted in order to extract meaning from the data gathered in the course of the research work.

The questionnaires was administered randomly in the study area to gather the required data from the insuring public and the insurance company and the data gathered were analyzed to answer the research questions based on the processed data.

5.1 SUMMARY

This project started from chapter one in which there was introduction of claim settlement. later, the statement of the problem was identified, the purpose of the study was established, the significance of the study was stated, which also entails the scope of the study and the limitations of the research as time constraint was part of it.als other research hypothesis was also stated.

Chapter 2 was on literature review. This chapter reviewed various previous work done on this study likewise references were made to write-ups, textbook, different books and journals for the purpose of the work, also there are various subtopics in this chapter.

Chapter 3 centered on the methodology of the research which entails the preamble, research design, population of the study, sample procedure and sample size, data collection instrument, method of data analysis and limitation of study.

Chapter 4 was on the presentation of data gathered through questionnaire, presented through a frequency table and further cross-tabulated.

5.2 CONCLUSION

Even though the demand for certain insurance policies might have been affected by contractual and legal requirements such as Bond, Motor, Workmen's Compensation Insurances etc, the results of the analysis of data as presented in chapter four showed that prompt and satisfactory claims settlement has positive effects on the sales and marketing of insurance products and vice versa. This confirmed the supposition by the researcher that the current image of the insurance industry in Nigeria and the consequent effects on the economies of Nigeria may be unconnected with the poor claims administration. This inference drawn from the results of the analysis of the study data is supported by opinions strongly held by some authorities;

In a paper presented before the Image Committee of the Chartered Insurance Institute of Nigeria (CIIN), Irukwu (2000) concluded that, "claim settlement must be done promptly and equitably because the best form of advertisement for insurance companies is prompt claims settlement." Several years earlier, Green (2000) in his write up in Annals of the Society of Chartered Property and Casualty Underwriters stated that, "Public perception of the industry (Insurance) is bound to affect the attitudes of the insuring public". According to him, "Any industry, whose market is affected by public opinions as insurance, certainly must learn, as much as it can, about the forces affecting public opinions if it is to operate successfully."

"To all intents and purposes, the claim department can be seen as the 'shop window' of the insurance company. It does not matter how cheap an insurance company's premium is, or how efficiently they conduct their underwriting administration, if a claim isn't handled properly and fairly. This is where an insurer will be judged." (Roff, 2004)

Therefore, it follows that prompt claims settlement has a significant influence on the purchase and repurchase of comprehensive motor insurance and insurance products as a whole.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

Having researched on the topic “effect of prompt claims settlement on the sales of comprehensive motor insurance policies in Nigeria”, as a solution to the slow settlement of claim leading to the poor image of the industry. The researcher hereby make the following recommendations which will be helpful in re-shaping the image of the insurance industry and also serve as a panacea to the adverse effect of unsatisfied customer of the insurance company..

However, there is the need to improve on the image of Insurance Company, which will lead to the growth of the company and the insurance industry as a whole.

From this research findings and conclusions, it has been established that claims administration affects the sales of insurance products.

Consequently, measures directed at running efficient and effective claims administration would go a long way in addressing the image problem of the industry.

It is in line with this that the following recommendations are made:

- Claims must be settled promptly and equitably in order to earn the confidence of customers and to retain their loyalty. Reducing documents required to process a claim and minimize correspondence and claims communication and reporting could do this.
- Where ex-gratia payment is made, insurance companies should use it as a launch pad for an effective public relations campaign through publication in the mass media.
- The underwriting and claims personnel in insurance companies should be trained properly in order to appreciate the sensitive nature and the role claims play in the insurance industry.
- Insurance companies should create and improve on their Customer Service Units so that complaints and suggestions can be promptly addressed.
- INSURANCE COMPANIES should undertake claims satisfaction research regularly. This would keep them abreast of the extent of customers' satisfaction, which will enable them to adopt better approach to claims settlement.

REFERENCES

Green, M. (2000). *Insurance and Public Image*, Annuals of the Society of Chartered Property and Casualty Underwriters, pp 250-293

Irukwu, J. (1977). *Insurance Management in Africa*. The Caxton press (West Africa) Ltd., Ibadan, pp.13-20.

Roff, N.A. (2004). Chartered Insurance Institute (CII) Coursebook, *Insurance Claims Handling Process*, CII Learning Solutions, Pp 1/2 -1/4

Dear respondent,

Odesanya Misturah Abimbola is interested in knowing “**The Effects of Prompt Claims Settlement on the Sales Comprehensive Motor Insurance in Nigeria**” as part of an academic work. I would therefore be grateful if you could kindly answer the under-listed questions in all honesty. Your responses would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank You.

SECTION A RESPONDENT BIODATA (Please tick the appropriate answer)

1. Sex: Male Female
2. Ages: 18-30 31-40 41-50 51-60 Above 60
3. Marital Status: Married Single
4. Educational Background: Primary Secondary Tertiary Professional

SECTION B

1. Do you have any motor insurance policy? Yes No
2. Please tick the type(s) of policy?
Acts only Third party fire and theft
Third party only comprehensive
3. For how long have you had the policy (ies)? Less than 2 years 2-5 years
6-9 years above 9 years
4. How did you get to know about insurance? Friends
Relations Agent/Broker Media Publicity (Fairs, Exhibitions)
5. Do you have any friends/relatives currently insured? Yes No
6. Have you ever made any claim on your insurance Policy (ies)? Yes No
7. Was this claim settled by the insurance company? Yes No
8. How long did it take the insurance company to settle the claim?
Within 1 week 2 weeks 3-4 weeks 5-6 weeks 6-8 weeks
9-12 weeks above 12 weeks
9. How long did you expect the settlement to take?
Within 1 week 2 weeks 3-4 weeks 5-6 weeks 6-8 weeks
9-12 weeks above 12 weeks

10. Was the amount paid equal to the claim estimate submitted by you? No Yes
Indifferent
11. To what extent were you satisfied with the claim amount paid? Not Satisfied
Satisfied Very Satisfied Indifferent
12. To what extent were you satisfied with the length of time taken to settle the claim?
Not Satisfied Satisfied Very Satisfied Indifferent
13. How would you describe the claim handling procedure of the company?
Satisfactory Very satisfactory Poor Very poor
14. Has the insurance company ever declined your claim at any time? Yes No
15. Were you given any reason(s) by the company as to why your claim was declined?
Yes No
16. What were the reason(s) given? Breach of policy condition Loss not covered by Policy
Lack of insurable interest Delay in notification
17. Were you satisfied by the reason(s) given for the decline of your claim? Yes No
18. Did you have any customer service machinery to lodge a complaints or an appeal?
Yes No
19. Will you continue to maintain your policy in spite of your Claim being declined? Yes No
20. Did you expect the claim to be paid? Yes No
21. Do you intend to take a policy or buy another Insurance policy (ies) from the company?
Yes No
22. Would you recommend to others to insure with the company given your experience?
Yes No
23. Have you been paying Insurance premium without making a claim on your policy (ies)?
Yes No
24. Will you continue to maintain your policy even when you have not been making claim?
Yes No

QUESTIONNAIRE TO STAFF OF THE COMPANY

Dear Sir/Madam,

As part of the requirement for the Award of Bachelor of Science in Insurance from University of Lagos, Ms. Odesanya Misturah Abimbola is conducting a research on **“The Effects of Prompt Claims Settlement on the Sales of Comprehensive Motor Insurance in Nigeria”** as part of an academic project work. I would therefore be grateful if you could kindly answer the under-listed questions in all honesty. Your responses would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank You.

SECTION A

1. Name of Respondent (Optional):.....
2. Sex: Male Female
3. Position of the person providing answers to the question:
4. Number of years worked with the company? 1-3 yrs 4-7yrs 10-15yr

SECTION B

1. When was your Company established?
2. Do you underwrite Comprehensive motor insurance? Yes NO
3. How long does it take on the average to settle claims after notification and documentation?
Within 3months 3-6months 6-9 months 9-12 month above 12 months
4. What are the responses of claimants to No. 3 above? Satisfied Not satisfied
Indifferent
5. Do claimants who have been settled come back to renew their policy (ies)? Yes No

6. Has there been any increase in the number of policies written in the last 3 years
 Yes No
7. Is the increase in the number of policies written by your company as a result of quality of
 Your claim services? Yes No
8. Have you ever declined to settle a claim? Yes No
9. If yes, on what ground(s) was the claim declined? Lack of insurable interest
 Breach of policy condition Unpaid premium others
10. Do claimants whose claim have been declined come back to renew their policy (ies)?
 Yes No
11. Has there been occasions when you had to pay amounts less than that claimed by your
 Customers? Yes No
14. Do you have any Complaints Service Unit where claimants can lodge their complaints?
 Yes No
15. Do you have any system of customer feedback after claims settlements? Yes No
16. Do you undertake on-going claims satisfaction research? Yes No